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ЦЕНзуРА В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ИСТОРИИ

Аннотация: Данная статья посвящена цензуры в современной истории кинематографии, анализ сегодняшнего состояния цензуры в истории кино

Ключевые слова: минусы, влияние, восточная кинематография, цензура, восточные принципы, культура, мораль, менталитет.

CENSORSHIP IN MODERN HISTORY

Abstract: This article is devoted to censorship in the modern history of cinematography, an analysis of the current state of censorship in the history of cinema

Key words: advantages, impact, Eastern cinematography, censorship, Eastern principles, culture, morality, mentality.

The international non-governmental organization Committee to Protect Journalists conducted a study on 10 criteria:

- Absence and/or restriction of private or independent media
- Criminal defamation laws, criminal restrictions for spreading false news
- Website blocking
- Jamming foreign broadcasts
- Blocking foreign correspondents
- Surveillance of journalists by the authorities
- Restrictions on the movement of journalists
- Requirements for obtaining a license to conduct journalism
- Restrictions on electronic recording and distribution
- Targeted hacking or trolling campaigns

and identified eleven countries with the most severe censorship:

1. Eritrea
2. North Korea
3. Turkmenistan
4. Saudi Arabia
5. China
6. Vietnam
7. Iran

8. Equatorial Guinea

9. Belarus

10. Cuba

11. Russia

History of censorship:

Censorship in the world appeared in the era of antiquity. Plato himself argued that the creator needs to have internal, personal censorship, which, coupled with a set of prohibitions of public censorship, could protect people from the destructive influence of works of art. Burning of philosophical and other books, bans on writings and teachings, persecution of people whose views were imbued with free-thinking - all these were attributes of censorship long before it was widespread.

Over time, the issue of censorship has evolved, attracting both people who see strict censorship as a necessity and those who see it as pointless and oppressive. The beginning of the 20th century created a new leap in restrictions, making censorship a weapon of totalitarian regimes and putting it at the service of propaganda. Warehouses of forbidden literature began to appear. The development and widespread dissemination of information technology has given impetus to the emergence of new types of censorship that controls all new sources of information. At this point, the world history of censorship is approaching the turn of our days. It exists in all modern states, on an official or unofficial level, but its true purpose remains vague in the eyes of ordinary people, which gives rise to many protests, discussions and reflections on the expediency.

According to the doctor of historical sciences T. M. Goryaeva, censorship arose at the moment when a group of people who had power and property began to impose their will on others. The very word "censorship" comes from the Latin. census, which meant in ancient Rome a periodic assessment of property to divide people into estates. The second meaning was related to the division according to the right to enjoy the privileges of citizenship. Thus, according to Goryaeva, the ancient censor monitored the reliability of the political orientation of citizens.

Censorship became an attribute of state and religious power in the era of antiquity. The Concise Jewish Encyclopedia cites the destruction of the scroll of Jeremiah's prophecies by the Jewish king Joachim (608-598 BC) as an example. The Encyclopedia Britannica notes that the books of the philosopher Protagoras on the gods were burned in Athens (480-410 BC). Plato proposed to introduce a set of prohibitions that protect people from the harmful effects of works of art. He became the first thinker to substantiate the need to combine the artist's self-censorship with prior public

ensorship. Subsequently, censorship and repression for free thought became an integral part of the politics of the Roman Republic and the Roman Empire. In 213 BC. e. the Chinese Emperor Qin Shi Huang ordered all but medical, agricultural, and scientific books to be burned to protect the empire from the perceived danger of poetry, history, and philosophy.

The first censored lists go back to the unacceptable apocryphal books, a list of which was compiled in 494 AD. e. under the Roman Bishop (Pope) Gelasius I. Prior censorship of books was first introduced in 1471 by Pope Sixtus IV. This was followed by similar decisions of Pope Innocent VIII (1487) and the Lateran Council (1512).

Later, under Pope Paul IV in 1557, the Index of Forbidden Books (lat. Index librorum prohibitorum) was issued for the Inquisition Tribunals. This list was canceled only in 1966. And in 1571, Pope Pius V established the Lat. "Congregatio Indicis", according to which no Catholic, under pain of excommunication, could read or keep books that were not included in the list specified by the pope. On the fires of religious censorship, not only banned books, but also their authors were often burned. The period of the Church Reformation was also notable for its intolerance of dissent. The European society of that time was infected with aggressive xenophobia, and the authorities supported church censorship through administrative, judicial and forceful measures.

Subsequently, critics of censorship appeared, for example, Pierre Abelard, Erasmus of Rotterdam and Michel Montaigne, who began to express doubts about its usefulness and expediency. Supporters of a strict form of censorship were Bernard of Clairvaux, Martin Luther and Tommaso Campanella. During the Age of Enlightenment, philosophers and politicians proclaimed the ideas of freedom of speech, press, and assembly. Brit The English philosopher Thomas Hobbes believed that if a church ban is not confirmed by state law, it is nothing more than advice. The poet John Milton, speaking in the English Parliament on June 16, 1643, for the first time specifically considered the features of censorship as a public institution. His critical treatise, *The Areopagitica*, hastened the abolition of prior censorship in England, which took place in 1695.

Most modern thinkers (for example, B. Constant, D. S. Mill, A. de Tocqueville and others) believed that due to changes in historical conditions, public opinion began to largely perform censorship functions. By the middle of the 19th century, prior censorship had been abolished in most of Europe. In the Russian Empire, on the contrary, since the second half of the 19th century (since the reign of Alexander III),

freedom of the press has been significantly reduced. This time went down in the history of journalism as an era of a large number of repressions against publishers.

At the end of the 19th and beginning of the 20th centuries, the first special stores appeared, where literature with limited access was stored, and along with them, illegal libraries of uncensored literature, or libraries located outside the country, began to be created. Subsequently, the special stores increased many times over, and by the end of the existence of the USSR, some of them contained up to half a million copies of books and periodicals.

In the 20th century, totalitarian regimes made censorship part of the repressive apparatus, mass manipulation and propaganda. Soviet censorship was under the complete control of the Communist Party and was of an ideological nature. The Nazi Propaganda Ministry controlled all media in Germany. Any dissent that contradicted Nazi ideas or threatened the regime was destroyed in all published sources.

In 2014, human rights activist Agnes Kalaman said in her speech at the UN Headquarters:

“The biggest humanitarian catastrophes that have brought man-made suffering to mankind for centuries — the Inquisition, the slave trade, the Holocaust, the Soviet Gulag, the genocide in Cambodia or Rwanda — not only included, but actually required absolute control over the expression of opinion, thoughts, sometimes even conscience. Hatred needs and is supported by censorship, and censorship, in turn, is necessary to nurture incitement to commit atrocious crimes.”

With the advent of new means of information transmission (in particular, electronic - radio, television, Internet), new forms of censorship have arisen. The need to control information coming from abroad led to the emergence of means of "jamming" radio broadcasts and Internet censorship. The USSR carried out jamming of "anti-Soviet broadcasting" for almost 60 years, with great intensity - 40 years. The difficulties of censorship control over information on the Internet have led some countries (for example, China and North Korea) to exercise total control over information passing through the junction of national Internet networks with world ones, and Iran has stated that it plans to completely isolate the internal network. As noted by the Intergovernmental Council of the UNESCO International Program for the Development of Communication, international law allows prior censorship only in exceptional circumstances, such as a certain threat to the main national interests of the state. However, some countries that have signed and ratified international treaties relating to freedom of speech still continue to impose prior controls in violation of their own laws or constitutions.

In 1988, Indian-born British writer Salman Rushdie published *The Satanic Verses*. Islamic organizations considered it blasphemous and blasphemous. In 1989, the spiritual leader of Iran, Ayatollah Khomeini, sentenced the writer to death and called on Muslims around the world to fulfill this fatwa. For 2021, the death sentence for a literary work against Rushdie has not been canceled, and the writer lives under the protection of special services.

However, in some democratic countries there are censorship restrictions on the demonstration of violence, and even more so calls for it, age restrictions for information of a sexual nature, etc. According to the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950, it is allowed to restrict the freedom of the press for reasons of national security or for establishing public order.

LITERATURE

1. Алексеев Игнатий. Цензурный инфантилизм. Призывы ввести цензуру — попытка Церкви переложить свою работу на «власть» или признак отчаяния и паники? Портал-Credo.Ru (16 марта 2007). Дата обращения: 15 декабря 2020. Архивировано 12 мая 2021 года.

2. Горяева Т. М. Политическая цензура в СССР. 1917-1991. — 2. — М.: «Российская политическая энциклопедия» (РОССПЭН), 2009. — С. 8—9. — 407 с. — (История сталинизма). — 2000 экз. — ISBN 978-5-8243-1179-2., стр 118

3. Ольга Демидова. Дмитрий Полознев: «При Сталине девки были моложе». Журнал «Библиотечное дело». СПб.: Агентство Информ-Планета. Дата обращения: 1 января 2019. Архивировано 2 января 2019 года.

